

Spectroscopic characterization of laser-induced luminescence for remote environmental thermometry

H. MUSTAFA,^{1,2,*} A. NEXHA,³ T. KISTER,³ H. BARTHOLOMEUS,¹
T. KRAUS,^{3,4} AND L. KOOISTRA¹

¹Laboratory of Geo-Information Science and Remote Sensing, Wageningen University and Research, 6708 PB Wageningen, The Netherlands

²Chair of Laser Processing, Department of Mechanics of Solids, Surfaces & Systems (MS3), University of Twente, 7522 NB Enschede, The Netherlands

³INM-Leibniz Institute for New Materials, Campus D2.2, Saarbrücken, Germany

⁴Department of Chemistry, Saarland University, Campus B2.2, Saarbrücken, Germany

*h.mustafa@utwente.nl

Abstract: Lanthanide-doped upconversion microparticles (UCMP) enable composites for luminescence thermometry with long luminescence lifetime and narrowband absorption and emission spectra. Being non-toxic, easily synthesizable, and having a bright, stable emission makes them an attractive candidate for in-vivo monitoring of key environmental parameters such as temperature. We use them to create soft, biodegradable, miniaturized seed-like robots endowed with fluorescence tags for the sustainable environmental monitoring of topsoil and air above soil environments. Our aim is an airborne platform with a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio to identify the concentration of targeted soil parameters. Here, we study the photoluminescence of Er, Yb: NaYF₄ UCMPs embedded in polylactic acid (PLA) polymeric matrix to assess their suitability for remote read-out. We assessed the signal-to-noise ratio in terms of excitation intensity, UCMP concentration, working distance, and sample orientation. We evaluated the signal stability over long exposure time as well as for amplitude-modulated excitation. Finally, we carried out ratiometric and lifetime measurements of luminescence emission in order to demonstrate the feasibility of such sensors in measuring the variation of temperature. Overall, the rare-earth doped UCMPs embedded in biodegradable polymer can be used for remote thermometry, displaying a significant signal-to-noise ratio for luminescence emission detection and subsequent derivation of temperature.

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1. Introduction

Non-contact luminescent thermometers are continuously replacing the traditional contact thermometers [1]. These non-contact thermometers solve crucial challenges, not addressed by the traditional thermometers. They can operate in harsh mediums, including biological fluids, electromagnetic fields, cryogenic temperatures and fast-moving objects, without hampering their performance [2]. Due to these, these thermometers allow remote readouts and provides high spatial resolution in short acquisition times with high temperature resolutions [2].

Among multiple materials for luminescent thermometry, such as organic dyes, proteins, semiconductors, and polymers [3], lanthanide doped particles are paving the way towards future developments in this field. That is due to their peculiar electronic configurations. Lanthanide doped materials exhibit very stable and narrow emission profiles, which cover a wide range of the electromagnetic spectrum, ranging from ultraviolet (UV), visible (Vis), near infrared (NIR) and short wavelength infrared (SWIR) lights. Lanthanide ions are barely non-toxic, and in addition,

often their emission wavelengths are triggered by NIR irradiation, which portrays a low-cost excitation source widely available.

When exposed to temperature, the characteristics of the photoluminescence of the lanthanide doped materials are tuned. In total, six parameters of the photoluminescence could be tuned with the change of temperature. Mainly, band-shape, intensity, bandwidth, spectral shift, lifetime, and polarization are varied as the temperature of the surrounding is changed. All these lead to six different ways of determining temperature [3]. Among these six, band-shape (or as also referred to ratiometric) and lifetime thermometry, are emerging as reliable techniques [4,5]. This is due to the fact that they are less affected by external factors, for example, the light arising from the surrounding environment where the thermometers are exposed, and they require simple optical setups to acquire data [3]. Nevertheless, despite being at the core of the developments on thermometry, these techniques are currently limited only within indoors.

In remote sensing, the photoluminescence of optical materials is exposed to different atmospheric conditions, involving acquiring data as a function of the working distance. In these outdoor conditions, the photoluminescence signal could be collected passively, *i.e.* from excitation from the solar irradiation and using detectors [6,7]. However, in an active laser-based photoluminescence detection, the interplay between the emitter and the detector plays a crucial role. In comparison with classical light detection and ranging (LiDAR) involving elastic scattering, laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) LiDAR is limited due to the nature of inelastic scattering, which is manifested in several orders of lower magnitude, omnidirectional emission, atmospheric interference in Vis range and atmospheric absorption at SWIR regions [8]. Therefore, tackling an acceptable signal to noise ratio (SNR) of the photoluminescence outdoors, requires careful and precise design of the LIF-LiDAR system.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) technology seems to be the solution to this limitation. In combination with photogrammetry processing, UAVs can provide more flexible and low-cost options when compared to conventional methods [9]. As a result, this aerial survey method can be significantly cheaper and faster than other methods, such as satellite based and terrestrial surveys. Additionally, UAVs provide significant flexibility in terms of cost, revisit-time, spatial resolution and operational resilience contrary to high-altitude platforms [10]. Regardless, integrating the LIF system into UAVs, particularly small sized ones, is challenging. Apart from the appropriate sensitivity of the detection system, the excitation laser source should have higher intensity to overcome background solar radiance during daytime operation. Although other solutions have been investigated, such as nighttime operations, they are limited in terms of precise geo-localization [11–13]. Up to date, active remote sensing for emission-based spectroscopy is limited to organic substances, including chlorophyll fluorescence from vegetations [14–16], from microalgae and aquatic environment [7,17], fossils [13], oil pollution [12,18], organic dye detection [11] and biodiversity monitoring [19]. However, work on airborne active emission spectroscopy of inorganic material is scarce. For example, Wiens et al developed Organicam for Martian cave exploration and detection of the luminescence of the lanthanide ions to distinguish from bio-organic materials with a maximum working distance of 5 m [20]. Other examples involve the development of a laser remote sensing instrument for Raman emission of geological rocks in a working distance of 20 cm [21], or designing a UAV for detection of chemical, biological and explosive (CBE) agents in ambient conditions within a distance of 10 m [22].

Seeds of natural plants (for example Samara seeds [23]) are a source of inspiration to design artificial soft robots that are able to monitor environmental parameters in a bioinspired fashion. These soft robots are composed of biodegradable polymers as polylactic acid (PLA), and a fluorescent unit made of lanthanide doped particles [23,24]. These soft robots will be deployed using UAVs, followed by spreading by the wind, as the natural seed do, and falling horizontally into the ground. They have to be detected in real time and the photoluminescence arising from the lanthanide doped particles, will be read to determine, for example, the temperature of the topsoil

[23]. For the remote readout, an active laser-induced fluorescence observation system onboard the UAV will irradiate the soft robots and collect the photoluminescence [25]. The designed UAV system should be able to collect the photoluminescence, geolocalize the photoluminescence in spatial coordinates, and estimate the altitude of the photoluminescence. These functions should account also for the weight, resolution and the SNR of the designed system.

Here, we identify key optical parameters of the unit composing the soft robots, composites of the lanthanide doped microparticles (UCMP) that will serve as benchmark for the design of the UAV system. We test the optical response of the composite as a function of the power density of the excitation, working distance, the concentration of the UCMP and orientation of the composite. The SNR is used as a figure of merit to evaluate the effect of these parameters. Finally, the fluorescent composites were employed as luminescent thermometers using the changes on the band shape and lifetime as a function of temperature.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Excitation source

The laser-induced fluorescence experiments were performed using a broad-area semiconductor laser source (LSR980NL3W of Civil Laser, PRC). This continuous-wave (CW) laser source emits randomly polarized light at a wavelength of 980 ± 5 nm with a maximum output power of 3.2 W and a power instability of $< 1\%$. The laser beam shows a Gaussian intensity profile along the fast and slow axis of the line-shaped beam (divergence 6.4 and 0.2 mrad respectively). A half wave plate (HWP) along with a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) cube was used to control the output power of the laser, as well as to polarize the beam linearly with an extinction ratio of 13.7 dB (see Fig. 1(a)). A pyroelectric detector (S405C with PM100D of Thorlabs, USA) was used to measure the average laser power after the beam passed through the HWP-PBS arrangement with an error less than 5%. The laser can be modulated up to a frequency of 30 kHz. The laser beam intensity profile was measured using a silicon charge-coupled device (CCD) sensor-based beam diagnostic system (SP920s with WB-I of Ophir Pho-tonics, USA). The excitation intensity I reported in this work are calculated from the measured average output power close to the beam exit, P divided by the cross-sectional beam area at the distance of the target position as:

$$I = \frac{P}{(\pi * d_{maj} * d_{min} / 4)}, \quad (1)$$

where d_{maj} and d_{min} are the beam diameter along the major and minor axis measured using the beam profiler. The beam profile is nearly Gaussian along both the axis.

2.2. Sample preparation and mounting platform

The green emitting composites were prepared via a solvent evaporation process, as reported previously [23]. Shortly, the polymer (polylactic acid, 1 g) was dissolved in apolar solvent (chloroform, 10 mL) using vortexing and ultrasound. The green emitting particles, as powder, were added (10 wt%) to the dispersion of the polymer. After stirring for about 0.5 h, homogeneous dispersion was obtained. A disc-shaped fluorescent composite, having a diameter of 1.7 cm and a thickness of 2.5 cm (see Fig. 1(b)), was produced after depositing 2 mL of the dispersion into a Teflon template, followed by allowing to dry at room temperature. The samples were placed at distance of 4 m from the laser source and the beam was directed perpendicular to the sample surface unless otherwise stated (see Sec. 3.1.4 for an exception).

Lanthanide-doped materials have the ability to absorb low energy photons and transfer it to high emitting energy. This process is called upconversion. These materials consists of a host, an activator and a sensitizer [26]. Er:Yb NaYF₄ are typical lanthanide upconverting materials. They are composed of a host matrix hexagonal NaYF₄ (β -NaYF₄), an activator Er³⁺, and Yb³⁺

Fig. 1. (a) Schematics of experimental setup. (b) PLA embedded UCMP sample discs. (c) Energy diagram of Er,Yb:NaYF₄ UCMP particles. (d) Thermal images of the heating/cooling stage with sample at 5 °C (left), 24 °C (center) and 41 °C (right).

a sensitizer Yb^{3+} . [27–29]. In such a configuration, Yb^{3+} sensitizer acts as excitation energy absorber that transfers energy to Er^{3+} activator resulting in higher luminescence efficiency. Figure 1(c) shows the schematic of energy exchange process in $\text{Er}:\text{Yb NaYF}_4$. Such a system exhibits absorption of excitation energy at 980 nm by Yb^{3+} sensitizers stimulating $^2\text{F}_{7/2} - ^2\text{F}_{5/2}$ (yellow lines), followed by energy transfer processes (gray lines) from sensitizer Yb^{3+} to activator Er^{3+} as well as within the sublevels of Er^{3+} ion. The subsequent relaxation of excited electrons follows multi-phonon assisted decays and spontaneous radiative and nonradiative transitions. The green arrows show the thermally coupled sublevels within Er^{3+} ions, whereas the red lines indicate the Stark split levels. For emission in the green, the electrons undergo a transition from $^4\text{I}_{11/2} - ^4\text{F}_{7/2}$, and due to instability of the $^4\text{F}_{7/2}$ level, relaxes non-radiatively to $^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ and $^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ and consequently returns to ground state by emitting green light. Similarly, the excited electron, through multiple transitions, emits blue and red light upon relaxation. Such transitions suggest that the green and red upconversion follows a two-photon process [29], whereas the blue upconversion follows a three-photon process [30]. With increasing temperature, the electron population at thermally coupled levels follows a different distribution, that is, the higher energy level $^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ has greater electron density than lower $^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ level [31]. As a consequence, the peak intensity ratio at these two wavelengths in green can be used to measure the temperature.

The samples were irradiated at controlled room temperature (21 ± 1 °C), as well as at temperatures of 5 ± 1 °C to 40 ± 1 °C to account for the probable temperature variation range in the agricultural fields or representative outside environment/conditions. For controlling the sample temperature above or below the room temperature, the samples were placed on an air to plate heat pump assembly (THP68B of Thermo Electric Devices, UK) using clamping arms (see Fig. 1(d)). The fluorescence emission from the samples was measured at a distance of 4 m for varying excitation intensities at an integration time of 3s and temperatures ranging from 5 to 40 °C to account for the probable temperature variation range in the agricultural fields or representative outside environment/conditions (see Fig. 1(a) for experimental setup). To verify the heating/cooling stage temperature, the temperature of the sample as well as the heating/cooling stage was monitored using a thermal camera (E6390 of FLIR, USA) as shown in Fig. 1(d). The spectroscopic measurements were performed when the sample temperature reaches equilibrium with the heating/cooling stage (see Fig. 1(d)). The excitation laser intensity was 2.3 W/cm^2 for CW-mode operation, and 1.0 W/cm^2 for modulated operation at 30 Hz.

2.3. Read-out

The emitted fluorescence was recorded by a general-purpose spectrometer with a back-thinned CCD array, having a 10 μm entrance slit and a grating of 821 lines/mm blazed at 450 nm (OCEAN-HDX-VIS-NIR of Ocean Insight, USA). The fluorescence light is collected by a Φ 2" 180 mm achromatic lens (AC508-180-AB-ML of Thorlabs, USA) in combination with a 10 mm collimating lens (74-VIS of Ocean Insight, USA) screwed onto a SMA-terminated 1000 μm optical fiber (QP1000-2-UV-BX of Ocean In-sight, USA). The integration time was adjusted as per the requirements of the experiments. The acquired raw spectra were subtracted by the dark spectra first, and then a baseline correction procedure was implemented before filtering the spectra for noise. The varying baseline was regressed to multiple shifted window points using spline approximation and was smoothed with a moving average filter over a span of 5 datapoints. The samples were also imaged during laser irradiation (see Fig. 1(d)) using a progressive scan CCD camera (Marlin F145C2 of Allied Vision Technologies, Germany), equipped with a 50 mm lens (VS-5026VM of VS Technology, Japan). A 700 nm short wave pass filter (LS-700-F 509W of Corion, USA) was placed before the lens to eliminate the reflection of the laser beam from reaching the imaging sensor. The modulated response of the laser was sampled using a pellicle beam splitter (BP208 of Thorlabs, USA) in combination with a longwave pass filter (FELH0900 of Thorlabs, USA) and a variable gain Si Avalanche Photodiode (APD) (APD410A/M of Thorlabs,

USA). In combination with a shortwave pass filter, similar APD was placed at a distance of 0.5 m to record the fluorescence response from modulated laser excitation. The output of the APDs was recorded using an oscilloscope (54622D of Agilent, USA), and the laser was modulated using a function generator (8116A of HP, USA).

3. Results

Spectroscopic characterizations for remote sensing applications were carried out by analyzing first the factors affecting the signal-to-noise ratio, secondly the stability of the fluorescence emission and finally the temperature dependency of the fluorescence emission.

3.1. Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR)

The laser emits at excitation wavelength that transmits through the transmission optics, propagates in the atmosphere, and illuminates the target at an incident angle. The illumination area is defined by the divergence angle, beam spot size and range. The target material absorbs the laser irradiation, and depending on the fluorescent particle density, probability of emission and quantum yield, emits the characteristic fluorescence wavelength(s) in all directions. Part of the fluorescence emission, which falls within the receiver solid angle, is collected by the collection optics at the receiver. The collected fluorescence is then focused on the detector's active area, and subsequently through photoelectric conversion, read as electric signal. The number of photons N_S collected at the detector for a pulsed laser irradiation is given by [32],

$$N_S = \left[\left(\frac{E_p \eta_{tx}}{h\nu} \right) \times \alpha_{tr}(\lambda_{ex}) \right] \times [n_a \sigma_a] \times \left[\Delta R \times \alpha_{tr}(\lambda_{fl}) \times \eta_{rx} \times \left(\frac{\pi D^2}{4R^2} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

where E_p is excitation laser pulse energy, η_{tx} is transmission efficiency, α_{tr} is atmospheric transmission at excitation and fluorescence wavelengths (λ_{ex} and λ_{fl} respectively), n_a is the concentration of fluorescing particles, σ_a is fluorescence cross section at excitation wavelength, ΔR is the range resolution, η_{rx} is collection optics efficiency, D is receiver clear aperture diameter, and R is distance from target to receiver. The absorption of excitation laser intensity I_{ex} and the subsequent conversion to fluorescence emission I_{fl} is related through fluorescence quantum yield φ_{fl} and is expressed as [33],

$$I_{fl} = \varphi_{fl} \times (I_{ex} - I_{tr}) \quad (3)$$

where I_{tr} is the transmitted laser intensity which depends on the Bouguer–Lambert law for a scattering medium as [34],

$$I_{tr} = I_{ex} e^{-(\mu_{abs} + \mu_{scat} + \sigma_a n_a) \times d}, \quad (4)$$

where μ_{abs} and μ_{scat} are the absorption and scattering coefficients of the solvent medium, and d is the optical path length, i.e. thickness of the sample. For a CW laser system, we can rewrite Eq. (2) as:

$$P_{detector} = I_{fl} \times [A_{sample} \times \alpha_{tr}(\lambda_{fl}) \times \eta_{rx} \times \Omega_{rx}], \quad (5)$$

where A_{sample} is the area of fluorescent sample and Ω_{rx} is the solid angle of the receiver defined as $\frac{\pi D^2}{4R^2}$, and $P_{detector}$ is the power detected by the receiver (aka sensor) which can be expressed as [35],

$$N_S = P_{detector} \times t_{int} \times \eta_{detector} \times \frac{\lambda}{hc}, \quad (6)$$

where t_{int} is the integration/ exposure time of the detector, $\eta_{detector}$ is the quantum efficiency of the sensor, λ , h and c are the wavelength, Planck's constant and the speed of light respectively.

Substituting Eq. (2) - (4) in Eq. (5), we get

$$P_{detector} = I_{ex} \times \eta_{tx} \times \alpha_{tr}(\lambda_{ex}) \times \varphi_{fl} \times (1 - e^{-(\mu_{abs} + \mu_{scat} + \sigma_{ana}) \times d}) \times [A_{sample} \times \alpha_{tr}(\lambda_{fl}) \times \eta_{rx} \times \Omega_{rx}] \quad (7)$$

The transmitter and receiver optics efficiency, η_{tx} and η_{rx} respectively, depends on the optical configuration of the system [36]. Such efficiency term can be calculated from the transmission and reflection losses associated with the transmitter and receiver optics, and typically lies in the range of 0.4 to 0.7 [37]. The atmospheric transmission close to the earth surface is mainly affected by haze, fog, rain and snow [38]. Depending on the ratio of wavelength and the size of the atmospheric particles, absorptions as well as Rayleigh, Mie and geometric scattering will affect both the excitation and emission wavelengths. For example, the optical attenuation by haze and fog is an order of magnitude larger for wavelength smaller than 550 nm than for longer wavelengths within a visibility range less than 10 km [39]. In contrast, rain fall rates greater than 10 mm/hr allows only 6.7% of visible and IR wavelength transmission over a 1.8 km path [40]. Such attenuation by rain drops ranges from 1 dB/km to 10 dB/km for light rain (2.5 mm/hr) to heavy rain (25 mm/hr) at a wavelength of 950 nm [41]. Such environmental factors severely limit the UAV-based remote sensing and should be taken into account when laser-induced luminescence is collected in non-ideal weather conditions. Otherwise α_{tr} can be neglected as being close to one.

The noise in the signal depends on various factors, including but not limited to, background noise arising from the solar irradiation or indoor illumination and reflection from surfaces, thermal noise, photon noise, electronic noise, stray light, aberration and readout noise. The spectrometer detects the incident number of photons per count, which is the ratio of photon counts to the number of incident photon at 400 nm. The incident photons per count increases with integration time of the spectrometer as a multiple of detector linearity (93%). In absence of the fluorescence signal, the acquired spectrum, also referred to as dark spectrum, accounts for majority of the noises, except the photon noise, which is equivalent to the square root of incoming photons. Signal-to-Noise ratios (SNR) can then be calculated as the ratio of fluorescence intensity to background intensity at a particular wavelength. SNR can be improved by temporal and/or spatial signal averaging (square root of number of spectral scans and pixels respectively); however, no averaging technique was implemented, and the reported data is derived from raw spectrum. The overlap between the illumination and detection field of view is paramount to achieve maximum fluorescence signal intensity. Therefore, the optical setup was optimized by evaluating the dependency of fluorescence emission detection on the integration time of the spectrometer, spectral resolution of the grating, optical throughput of the slit, field of view of collection optics and the core diameter of the optical fiber.

3.1.1. Excitation power

Figure 2(a) shows typical spectra of green emitting composites (15 wt%), and the position of the peaks of interest for thermometry are marked with red arrow. The samples were placed at a distance of 4 m and the location of laser irradiation on the sample is shown in the inset of Fig. 2(a). Note that these PLA embedded UCMP samples were subjected to high laser intensity to determine the damage threshold of the samples. Within the limits of output laser power, these green emitters did not show any damage over a period of 90 min at an exposure of 3.15 W/cm². The dependency of PLA embedded fluorescing samples on the excitation laser power was also evaluated at a distance of 4 m, and with a spectrometer integration time of 100 ms. In accordance with Eq. (2), the SNR increases linearly with increasing laser power, owing to the increase of fluorescence signal with increasing excitation power. As can be observed from Fig. 2(b), no saturation of fluorescence intensity with increasing excitation laser intensity was observed within the limits of experiment. The slope of the curves for individual wavelengths of the fluorescence response can be fitted according to $I \propto P^n$ characteristics, where I is the

intensity of the fluorescence response, P is the excitation power, and n is the number of photons undertaking the upconversion process [42]. The logarithmic linear increase of luminescence with increasing power can be corroborated by the numerous observations [29,31]. The slope value n is close to 2 for 520 nm, 540 nm and 650 nm peaks indicating a two-photon absorption process [31,43]. Although the emission process for blue peak involves three-photon absorption, the value of n is close to 1, which is the case for high pumping power [29].

Fig. 2. (a) Typical spectra from green emitters at a laser intensity of 0.72 W/cm^2 at a distance of 4 m, collected with a spectrometer having an integration time of 0.5 sec and a FWHM spectral resolution of 0.73 nm. Inset shows the relief shading of the photograph of the sample overlaid with laser beam intensity profile. (b) Dependency of luminescence peak intensity on the excitation laser intensity at a distance of 4 m.

3.1.2. Filling ratio

Samples with varying filling ratios of UCMPs were characterized at an excitation intensity of 7.5 W/cm^2 , over a distance of 1.2 m and an integration time of 500 ms. In accordance with Eq. (4), luminescence emission increased exponentially with increasing filling ratio of UCMPs. As can be seen from Fig. 3(a), the signal intensity increased slightly with increasing fluorescing particle filling ratio from 1% to 8%, however, a sharp increase in peak intensity was observed when the particle filling ratio increases from 8% to 10%. Such behavior could result from the inhomogeneity in UCMP distribution within the solid samples. The PLA embedded samples were casted in small molds and cured solid. As can be seen from Fig. 3(b), the fluorescing particles were not evenly distributed within the solidified samples and the air-exposed side exhibits sharp edges with higher concentration of particles. A total of 16 samples having a UCMP filling ratio of 10 wt%, were analyzed for reproducibility and repeatability. As can be seen in Fig. 3(c), the samples resulted in varying degrees of signal intensity, and such non-uniformity gives rise to uncertainty in the measured signal. Despite the variations in the peak magnitudes, none of the spectra contained additional fluorescent features, which attest to the spectra homogeneity of the sample [44]. In operational condition, the UCMPs would be homogeneously mixed with PLA and would be casted in an automated manner. Such a procedure drastically reduces the uncertainty from sample to sample. Figure 3(d) show the spectra of homogeneously casted samples. When comparing the two aforementioned manufacturing procedure, it can be observed that the homogeneous samples show significantly lower spread around the peaks of interest (see the dashed black curve in Fig. 3(c)).

Fig. 3. (a) Luminescence peak intensities as a function of UCMP filling ratio in PLA embedded samples. Inset shows the peak intensities at 841 nm and 408 nm as a function of filling ratio. (b) Photograph of casted samples showing inhomogeneity in particle distribution. Scale bar indicates 10 mm. (c) Spectra of inhomogeneous samples at a distance of 4 m and a laser intensity of 0.72 W/cm². (d) Spectra of homogeneous samples at a distance of 4 m and a laser intensity of 0.92 W/cm².

3.1.3. Working distance

Figure 4 shows the normalized intensity of luminescence emission as a function of working distance. The diode laser source shows high divergence, therefore, the laser intensity for same output laser power reduces with increasing distance. The reduced intensity lowers the fluorescence emission which requires longer integration time to achieve similar intensity levels. Therefore, the collected spectra were normalized over integration time and excitation intensity. Note that such normalization is not ideal as the emission intensity is correlated with excitation intensity. The normalized data were then fitted according to Eq. (1), that is as a function of inverse distance squared. As can be observed in Fig. 4, the detected emission scales as $1/R^2$ with increasing distance with a goodness of fit parameter $R^2 > 90\%$. Since the graph is plotted in log-log scale, the deviation for lower intensity values appears larger. In addition, the adherence to inverse of squared distance $1/R^2$ relationship deviates with emission intensities of different wavelength (see Fig. 2(e)). That is the weaker emission at 408 nm deviates less and the stronger emission at 541 nm deviates more from inverse squared relationship with distance. The reason for such observation would be fluorescence anisotropy in semi-transparent medium with increasing optical depth [45]. The Lambertian approximation of fluorescence emission is only valid for the emission from the surface. With increasing optical depth, fluorescence emission becomes strongly anisotropic. Since shorter wavelengths are scattered and reabsorbed more than longer wavelength, the deviation from inverse-square law happens to a lesser extent for 408 nm than stronger 541 nm response.

Fig. 4. Normalized fluorescence peak intensities as a function of working distance.

3.1.4. Sample orientation

Excitation laser intensity will be reduced for non-normal sample orientation, as the irradiated beam area gets asymmetrically elongated towards the inclined plane. A reduction in excitation intensity would reduce the fluorescence emission accordingly. The I-seeds will be released from an elevated altitude, and they will spread over the target area following their natural pathways. As a result, the target area will have a variety of land coverage, including but not limited to, concrete, soil, soil – grass mixture and grass of varying heights. Samara seeds are relatively small and will be viewed from an aerial perspective after landing on an uneven

surface at various angles (see Fig. 5(a)). As the complexity of the background increases (e.g., vegetated surfaces), the landing orientation and occultation of the I-Seeds by ground objects also increases. Different landing orientations other than normal to the surface will reduce the laser intensity (see Fig. 5(b)), while occultation from ground objects reduces the effective surface area available for excitation and readout of fluorescence emission. Additionally, in a bistatic configuration, the fluorescence emission is shadowed if the sample is inclined towards the opposite direction to the detector surface. Over the course of our experiments, it was found that the laser block screens, optomechanical holders and posts made from anodized Aluminum results in a broad-band reflection from 980 nm laser irradiation. Therefore, a baseline correction procedure was implemented before filtering the spectra for noise. The recorded, baseline corrected and filtered spectra at various sample orientation angle are shown in Fig. 5(c). As can be observed from the normalized intensities of the peaks shown in Fig. 5(d), the fluorescence emission intensity reduces with increasing incident angle when the samples are facing the detector. The reduction reduces according to the cosine law as also observed for vegetation fluorescence [46]. However, the effect of occultation on the peak intensities increases as the sample moves away from the detector. The effect of sample inhomogeneity of the recorded data in Fig. 5(d) is more apparent for the cases 'away' from the detector. As the tilting gets higher, shorter wavelengths experience higher scattering within the material than the longer wavelengths [47]. In addition, increased path length within the sample favors longer wavelengths since they suffer relatively less attenuation [48]. Moreover, the Lambertian approximation of fluorescence emission is only valid for the emission close to the surface and becomes strongly anisotropic within the depth of the sample [45]. Therefore, the higher the tilting angle, the more probable is the detection of longer wavelengths. This is also visible in Fig. 5(d) of the manuscript, that the longer wavelengths experience higher increase than shorter wavelengths, e.g. 46% increase for 654 nm than 5% increase for 540 nm.

3.1.5. Colorimetry

One of the spectroscopic methods of analysis is colorimetry, where the intensity of the electromagnetic radiation is typically measured over three overlapping broadband wavelength bands namely – B (400 nm - 550 nm), G (450 nm – 600 nm) and R (550 nm – 700 nm). As such a RGB color camera can be used to perform spectroscopic characterization if the peaks of interest are sufficiently distant from each other. LIF from I-Seeds is significantly stronger than the solar reflection from the objects. If there are saturated pixels within the region of interest (ROI), they would not bear any information. Such is the case when the camera settings are adjusted for a sharp image over the complete field of view (FOV). The most influencing parameter in this case is the exposure time of the camera. By appropriately adjusting the shutter triggering time, the background can be effectively removed (pixel value 0), while retaining the fluorescence part (see Fig. 6). Intuitively, the percentage of saturated pixels increases with increasing laser intensity, since fluorescence intensity increases with laser intensity, although shorter exposure time is possible at higher laser intensity. It should be noted that the exposure time and the gain of the camera should be kept fixed in order to perform spectral comparison between different experimental conditions. This is because the mapping of scene irradiance to image brightness is performed using non-linear camera response function (CRF) [49]. If the analytical expression of the CRF is determined, a lookup table (LUT) can be defined to compensate for the nonlinear brightness response. In the CIE 1931 chromaticity chart shown in Fig. 6(b), the chromaticity coordinates of sample with 15% UCMP filling ratio is shown for the region of interest marked white dashed circle in Fig. 6(a). With varying temperature, the location of the luminescence emission in the chromaticity plot does not change, however, this position varies significantly for increasing exposure time. After the I-Seeds are spread over the ground, and geolocalization is complete, the read-out of the sensors will take place. Between the time of geolocalization

Fig. 5. (a) I-Seed prototypes against different backgrounds. (b) Schematic of the effect of sample orientation on available excitation intensity of 1 W/cm². (c) Spectra of PLA embedded UCMP sample (10 wt%) at different orientation angles. (d) Normalized intensity of the fluorescence peaks as function of sample orientation angle.

after landing, and the readout of the sensors, the I-Seeds may be moved away from their original position by wind, surface runoff, birds and animals. The localization of the seeds before read-out thus becomes an important verification step.

Fig. 6. (a) RGB image of PLA embedded green fluorescent sample irradiated with excitation laser beam at varying exposure time. (b) CIE 1931 chromaticity plot for average pixel intensity in the region of interest.

3.2. Signal stability

The stability of the LIF signal over an hour was evaluated at a distance of 0.22 m for PLA embedded samples having 15% fluorescent particles. The peak intensity values in Fig. 7(a) were traced for the peak at 654 nm at an integration time of 100 msec. As is evident from Fig. 7(a), there is a transient state associated with LIF emission just after the exposure to laser irradiation before reaching a steady-state emission intensity. During the steady-state, deviation from the mean value is less than <1%. Zooming in into the first 4 mins (Fig. 7(b)), the emission overshoots just after being exposed to laser irradiation and then drops exponentially to a steady state value. The time required for settling to a steady-state value and the extent of signal overshoot above the steady-state value shows a linear trend with laser intensity (Fig. 7(c)). However, in any case, the minimum settling time is half a minute. During the 60 min irradiation time, the temperature of the sample was measured in non-contact mode using a handheld IR thermometer (Thermospot One of Laserliner, Germany), and no change from room temperature value of 20°C was observed. We evaluated the samples further to correlate the transient fluorescence emission behavior with the transmitted power. The power meter, equipped with a longwave-pass filter of 900 nm, was placed 10 cm in front of the sample to measure the incoming laser intensity and 6 cm behind the sample to collect the transmitted IR power. As shown in Fig. 7(d) and (e), the transmitted power through the sample and the fluorescence emission of the sample follows a similar, but opposite trend. That is – the excitation power is absorbed more strongly at the start of the exposure resulting in stronger emission and gradually increases to the steady state value while the emission decreases to steady state value. This behavior is similar for sample with 15 wt% as well as 1 wt% fluorescent particle. This observation indicates that the Er,Yb:NaYF₄ fluorescing particles requires a certain amount of time to reach a steady state emission value. From the operational point of view, this observation indicates that the readout strategy needs to be defined accordingly. In case of UAV flying over the target area at 1 m/s with laser on, the I-Seeds will be exposed to laser radiation for a max. of 5 ms. In case of drone hovering over the geolocalized seed location, the excitation time can be longer. To ensure a steady state emission value, the samples need to be exposed to laser radiation for at least half a minute for an excitation intensity less than 0.5 W/cm².

Fig. 7. (a) Peak tracing at luminescence emission wavelength of 654 nm for varying laser intensity over a period of one hour and (b) zoomed in for first 4 minutes. (c) Settling time (left) and signal overshoot (right) as a function of excitation intensity. (d) Luminescence emission at 654 nm at 12.93 W/cm^2 and transmitted IR power ($P_{in} = 3.25 \text{ W}$) as function of time for samples with 15 wt% and (e) 1 wt% UCMP particles. Insets show zoomed in graph for first 0.5 minutes.

Luminescence is a time dependent phenomenon, that is, it takes time to reach saturation, as well as, to terminate. Therefore, one of the important parameters of fluorescence is its lifetime, which is how long the sample fluorescence signal continues after the termination of laser excitation. We tested the single emitter (green, 15%) samples with modulated laser excitation to characterize the temporal response of LIF for Er,Yb:NaYF₄ fluorescing particles. As shown in Fig. 8(a), the laser was modulated (direct modulation) from 3 Hz up to 30 kHz (the maximum modulation frequency of the laser source), and the sample response was recorded using photodiodes from a distance of 0.5 m. At a distance of 4 m, the baseline shift of during the fluorescence response could be observed, but the edges of the signal are highly susceptible to background noise. In the simplest case, the fluorescence decay of an impulse excitation follows a single exponential behavior [50]. However, due to complex dynamics involved, the lifetime is calculated as summation of multiple exponentials as

$$I_{fl}(t) = \sum_i B_i e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}}, \quad (8)$$

where τ_i is the fluorescence lifetime, B_i is the pre-exponential factor and t is time. The lifetime of the fluorescence decay was estimated from 3 Hz and 30 Hz modulated excitation and was fitted with single and multiple exponentials. With single exponentials the lifetime was estimated to equal 855 μ s with a R² value of >95%. However, fitting with two exponential terms yield better result and gives two separate lifetimes as can be seen in Fig. 8(b). There is a fast decay of about 25 μ s, followed by a longer decay of 750 μ s. For modulation frequencies greater than 30 Hz, the fluorescence buildup didn't mature and thus does not yield any good fit. As can be seen for modulation frequency of 300 Hz in Fig. 8(b), the trend of fast decay followed by a long-lived emission was also visible in spite of the steady state buildup of emission. From 3 kHz and onwards, the laser diode does not have sufficient time to properly build up laser power (Fig. 8(b)), and therefore the modulated laser pulses start to deviate from square wave shape, resulting in similar trend in fluorescence emission (Fig. 8(a)). However, the fluorescence emission shows comparable decrease with excitation power. For example, for a decrease of excitation intensity by 95.3%, the fluorescence response recorded by the photo detector reduces by 95% (see 30 kHz response in Fig. 8(a)). Such a modulated read out has the capability of suppressing the background irradiation, overcoming the orientation angle dependence of the fluorescence signal intensity, and disregarding the intensity reduction of LIF due to the occultation by natural objects on the ground (e.g., vegetation, grass, litters, debris etc.).

3.3. Targeted parameter (temperature) variation

The PLA embedded fluorescing samples are made of Er,Yb:NaYF₄ fluorescing particles which appears green when excited and changes the emission intensity of the peaks at 520 nm and 540 nm with the change in sample temperature.

3.3.1. Intensity-shift based thermometry

For Er³⁺ doped materials, the thermally coupled levels ²H_{11/2} and ⁴S_{3/2} conforms to Boltzmann distribution law and are in thermal equilibrium. With increasing temperature the depopulation from ⁴S_{3/2} level to ²H_{11/2} level leads to the variation of relative intensities I_λ of green ($\lambda = 520$ nm) and yellowish green ($\lambda = 540$ nm) peaks in the emission spectrum [51]. The ratio of temperature dependent variation of peak intensity is known as Fluorescence Intensity Ratio (FIR) and follows an exponential law as [3],

$$FIR = \frac{I_{520}}{I_{540}} = A e^{-B/T} \quad (9)$$

where, A is a material-dependent constants, B is the ratio between the energy gap of the thermally coupled levels ΔE and Boltzmann constant k as $B = \Delta E/k$, and T is temperature. Usually, the area

Fig. 8. (a) Modulated laser excitation and corresponding sample fluorescence response for different modulation frequencies. (b) Fluorescence decay at different modulation frequency as a function of time. (c) Laser intensities at corresponding modulated frequencies.

under the curves at locations of I_λ are integrated over a spectral bandwidth of 10 nm for enhancing the signal-to-noise ratio, however, taking the maximum values of intensity at the two locations of I_λ also works if a dispersion of nanocrystals is used instead of single nanocrystals [51]. Such a thermometric approach using FIR falls within band-shape based thermometry. In this work, instead of integrating over two different spectral regions, we take the maximum intensity of the peak values. The fluorescence emission from the samples were measured at a distance of 4 m for varying sample temperature at a laser intensity of 0.6 and 1.8 W/cm². The intensity ratios are plotted in Fig. 9(a) and fitted to Eq. (9). The data indicates small but detectable change of fluorescence emission with changing temperature and varying excitation intensity at a distance of 4 m. It can also be observed that the FIR increases with increasing temperature conforming to the depopulation of ⁴S_{3/2} level to ²H_{11/2} level. The dependence of FIR on excitation intensity becomes evident from Fig. 2(b). As can be observed in Fig. S1(a) (Supplement 1), the n value for 520 nm and 540 nm are different, giving a relationship of $P^{-0.2}$ for the FIR. That is, with increasing excitation intensity, the FIR should drop (see the right axis of Fig. S1(a)). However, with increasing temperature, the occupancy in thermally coupled levels ²H_{11/2} and ⁴S_{3/2} are affected differently. At low excitation intensity, the peak intensity of 520 nm rises linearly (see Fig. S1(c)), whereas the change in 520 nm is almost constant in case of high excitation intensity (see Fig. S1(b)). Consequently, at high excitation intensity, the contribution to increasing FIR with increasing temperature stems mainly from the decrease in the peak intensity of 540 nm. Therefore, FIR is affected not only by the power dependency, but also for different excitation mechanisms in the fluorescing particles. Such observations points to the importance of proper calibration of the UCMP embedded biodegradable polymer in FIR based thermometry. To verify the laser-induced thermal effects, thermographic images were captured during the experiment (see Fig. 1(c) – (e)), and we did not observe any specific temperature variation of the sample arising from laser irradiation.

Fig. 9. Spectroscopic measurements of temperature variation of the PLA embedded UCMP sample (10 wt%) at a distance of 4 m – (a) Fluorescence intensity ratio as a function of temperature. (b) Maximum of RAW 8-bit value of red (R), green (G) and blue (B) pixels within the region of interest (ROI) as a function of temperature.

For intensity-based thermometry, we employ an RGB camera and evaluate the signal at the individual R, G and B channel. If the actual Bayer arrangement of the filter pattern is known, the pixel values associated with corresponding color filters can be extracted and plotted for varying temperature at a given laser intensity and working distance. It was found that within the limits of

exposure time for non-saturated pixels, 8-bit RAW data of R, G, and B pixels provides some insight on the sample temperature. Figure 9(b) shows the maximum ROI pixel values of R, G, and B pixels as a function of sample temperature for an exposure time of 146 μs . As can be observed in Fig. 9(b), G and R pixel values decrease with increasing temperature with a slope of 1.94 and 0.14 respectively. This means that for one degree of temperature change, the maximum value of G pixels within the ROI would drop by a factor of 2. Therefore, imaging would provide a cheap and faster alternative to approximate the temperature values of these artificial seed-like structures, in comparison to the non-imaging spectroscopy. Detailed information can be found in Ref. [25].

3.3.2. Temporal-shift based thermometry

Fig. 10. (a) Luminescence lifetime measurement for modulated excitation at a frequency of 30 Hz and an excitation intensity of 0.66 W/cm^2 from a distance of 0.5 m, showing the laser pulse (black dotted line) and the luminescence responses at 5°C (blue solid line) and 40°C (red solid line). The vertical dashed and dash-dotted lines represent the rise and settling times respectively. (b) The derivative of the luminescence responses shown in (a).

The luminescence lifetime was analyzed by modulating the laser source using a function generator and recording the filtered luminescence response using a Si-APD photodiode for a sample having 10% UCMP filling ratio. The laser modulation frequency was 30 Hz, and the luminescence response was recorded using a short-pass filter at 700 nm to exclude the laser reflection. The luminescence response curves at 5°C , and 40°C are shown in Fig. 10(a) along with the laser pulse. The rise time t_{rise} and settling time t_{settle} as shown in Fig. 10(a) refer to the signal intensity reaching $1/e$ times and 2% of the saturated value respectively. As can be observed, the rise and settling times increases by 21.4% and 65.6% respectively for an increase in temperature from 5°C to 40°C . The quenching, however, is not affected except for a delay in decay for lower temperature as shown by the red circle in Fig. 10(a). The decay time stays the same for both responses at low and high temperature. From the derivative of the luminescence responses shown in Fig. 10(b), the delay at the start of the decay is evident. However, the settling time increases by 2 ms for a temperature increase of 35 K, making the lifetime sensitivity to temperature change as $1.87\% \text{ K}^{-1}$. Lifetime-based thermometry using Er^{3+} , Yb^{3+} codoped nanoparticles has been successfully applied in various studies, and similar trends, that is, a decrease in lifetime for increasing temperature at an excitation wavelength of 980 nm was

reported by dos Santos et al., although their relative sensitivity is almost four times lower than our reported value [52]. Similar observation was also reported by Rafiei Miandashti et al. that shows decrease in lifetime for increasing temperature, and shows similar long lifetime in μs regime [53]. Additionally, recent findings by Ehtesham Raza et al. provide strong evidence that luminescence lifetime variation correlates reliably with temperature changes [54]. Our results align well with these previous works, supporting the validity of our approach. Although additional intermediate temperature data were not included in this study, the observed spectral shifts and their correlation with thermal effects are in agreement with established thermometric principles. Future studies will focus on a more detailed mapping of the lifetime-temperature trend to reinforce our findings.

4. Discussion

The material surrounding the fluorescent compounds strongly affects the features of electromagnetic spectra, as well as the energy dynamics of the fluorescing system [55]. The Lanthanide doped luminescence particles are embedded in natural transparent PLA polymer having a thickness of 2.5 mm. PLA is a weakly absorbing material, whose refractive index n can be determined using Cauchy's formula, and for a wide range stereoisomer proportions, it was reported to be $n(\lambda) = (1.445 \pm 0.00075) + (4892 \pm 143)/\lambda^2$ [56]. Because of the higher refractive index than air, the light rays will bend away from the surface normal, making the short-wavelength component of the fluorescence emission from the UCMPs even more diffuse. For the UCMPs deep within the PLA, reabsorption of short wavelengths might also take place [57]. In case of excitation wavelength at non-normal incidence, this would reduce the effective area of illumination along the depth of the semi-transparent PLA. Alongside, the absorption and scattering of light as it travels through the PLA takes place following modified Lambert-Beer law [58]. The extinction coefficient can then be expressed as the combination of absorption and scattering coefficients as $\mu = \mu_a + \mu_s$ and can be determined from the transmission measurements [59]. It should be noted that the optical properties of PLA are highly dependent on hydrolytic and thermal degradation, functionalization elements and dyes, which in turns determine the crystallinity of the solidified sample [60]. For a 2.5 mm thick PLA discs having 1 wt% UCMPs result in a transmission of 2.2% at a wavelength of 980 nm (see Fig. 7(d)), whereas similar transparent PLA extruded sheet having a thickness of 0.4 mm (approx. 6 times thinner) was reported to have a transmission of 20% [59]. Considering the additional absorption and scattering by the UCMPs, the transmission value seems to be in agreement. Following Lambert-Beer law, i.e. $\ln \frac{I}{I_0} = \mu d$, where I and I_0 are transmitted and incident intensity, and d is the thickness of the sample, the extinction coefficient μ amounts to 15 cm^{-1} at a wavelength of 980 nm. With the increase in filling ratio (i.e. concentration) of UCMPs, the transmitted power reduces accordingly. This is expected as the absorbance of UCMPs increases with increasing concentration [61]. However, the immediate overshoot of fluorescence response during laser exposure and the subsequent steady state response was omnivalent for all the sample concentration and excitation intensities. Such temporal evolution was also observed for Rhodamine B luminophore and was attributed to photobleaching [62]. However, over repeated exposure, we did not observe photobleaching of the sample, that is, the fluorescence intensity did not reduce over time due to the overshoot. In our case, the static fluorescence quenching can be attributed to the number of free Yb^{3+} molecules available for excitation [63]. Such a hypothesis can be corroborated with the excitation intensity dependence of the overshoot and the settling time (see Fig. 7(b)). The higher the excitation energy, the longer it takes to reach the steady state emission.

When light is absorbed by the UCMPs, the part that does not contribute to radiative energy transfer aka fluorescence is dissipated as resonant non-radiative energy, and the quantum yield depends on the fractional thermal loading resulting from resonant energy transfer [64]. For different types and sizes of $\text{NaYF}_4:\text{Yb}^{3+},\text{Er}^{3+}$ the reported quantum yield is less than 10% [65,66]. This means that the majority of the absorbed energy is dissipated following different quenching

pathways including nonradiative, multiphoton and cross relaxation [67]. For Lanthanide doped UCMPs, the resonant energy transfer efficiency can be as high as 25% [26]. This in return, increases the temperature of PLA surrounding the UCMP, also known as optical heating [68]. However, we did not notice damage to the samples, nor increase in sample temperature for exposure at maximum excitation intensity within the limit of our experimental work.

The temporal response of the luminescence emission is less affected by the uncertainties and complications mentioned so far. Such a quenching mechanism can be then described as static fluorescence quenching instead of dynamic process. The lifetime and lineshape of the response are unaffected except at temperature variation. However, the emission intensity drops by the inverse squared of distance (see Sec. 3.1.3) and therefore limits the measurement to relatively shorter distance.

Temperature variation can be monitored with relatively simple optical setup through intensity-shift based thermometry. However, numerous parameters affect the intensity of luminescence emission including but not limited to excitation intensity, sample concentration, sample orientation, polarization of the laser source, working distance and exposure time of the collection instruments such as camera and spectrometer. Therefore, detailed knowledge of these parameters become crucial for properly determining the temperature of the target. From an operational point of view, such dependencies make it difficult for accurate extraction of temperature in field scenario. On the other hand, temporal-shift based thermometry is not affected by the parameters that cause a change in emission intensity. Typically, relatively low-cost Avalanche Photodiodes (APDs) have significantly small active areas, which makes the measurement of temporal response challenging for larger distances due to the omnidirectional emission and dependency of optical signal strength over distance. Addressing such an issue requires expensive instruments such as Geiger-mode APDs, which also adds significant weight to the overall payload design for UAVs. Additionally, lifetime measurements inherently require high-level of synchronization between illumination and collection optics. In contrast, spectral measurements provide more insight into the energy dynamics of the UCMPs. Overall, the simplest and most lightweight solution is to make use of a RGB camera and colorimetry, but such approach also requires careful determination of camera exposure time.

5. Conclusions

A spectroscopic characterization study for laser-induced luminescence of sensors on biodegradable artificial seeds, so-called I-Seeds, was prepared to support future environmental thermometry applications. In the context of this I-Seed scenario, quantification of the emitted fluorescence signal strength from I-Seeds is important as it indicates the concentration or level of monitored environmental parameter. Several factors can affect the system's signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), and thereby, the actual development of the payload system start from a laboratory-based setup to achieve a complete understanding of the level of influence of these parameters for real-world field applications. We demonstrated the read-out of stable signal with good SNR up to a distance of 4 m in controlled laboratory conditions. Critical environmental conditions and sample behavior were assessed to evaluate their effect on signal read-out. Proof of principle for temperature read-out using both intensity-shift and temporal-shift based thermometry have been realized. We showed that the UCMP doped PLA samples shows good theoretical agreement in terms of excitation intensity, working distance and UCMP concentration. We also revealed several parameters such as sample orientation and signal stability, which influence the potential Signal-to-Noise ratio (SNR). We pointed out that homogeneous samples are a prerequisite for achieving a complete understanding of the level of influence of these parameters in a field scenario. All in all, we presented the capabilities of remote laser-induced luminescence observation system through lab-scale experiments, which paves the way for the development of lightweight prototype for field testing. As follow-up, complexities will be added to the laboratory and field set-up, including but

not limited to, repeating the measurements using a translational stage to imitate drone movement, effect of occultation in the field, using a mobile aerial working platform (cherry picker) to assess the effect of target distance and various land coverage, effect of vibration and instabilities in the mount on the device readout, and triggered excitation and acquisition. Consequently, after every step, effects on the measured fluorescence signal strengths will be evaluated and potential solutions or improvements for next iteration will be identified.

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Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) for supporting content.

References

1. C. Brites, A. Millán, and L. Carlos, "Lanthanides in luminescent thermometry," in *Handbook on the Physics and Chemistry of Rare Earths* (Elsevier, 2016), 49, pp. 339–427.
2. S. W. Allison and G. Gillies, "Remote thermometry with thermographic phosphors: Instrumentation and applications," *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **68**(7), 2615–2650 (1997).
3. A. Nexha, J. J. Carvajal, M. C. Pujol, *et al.*, "Lanthanide doped luminescence nanothermometers in the biological windows: strategies and applications," *Nanoscale* **13**(17), 7913–7987 (2021).
4. T. Eftimov, I. Kostova, A. Arapova, *et al.*, "Rise and decay time responses of Sr aluminate phosphorescent materials," *J. Lumin.* **235**, 117985 (2021).
5. P. Kumar, R. Patel, N. Shrivastava, *et al.*, "Aspects of luminescence nanoprobe for thermometry: Progress and outlook," *Applied Materials Today* **35**, 101931 (2023).
6. N. Wang, J. Suomalainen, H. Bartholomeus, *et al.*, "Diurnal variation of sun-induced chlorophyll fluorescence of agricultural crops observed from a point-based spectrometer on a UAV," *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* **96**, 102276 (2021).
7. A. B. Utkin, R. Felizardo, C. Gameiro, *et al.*, "Laser induced fluorescence technique for environmental applications," in *Second International Conference on Applications of Optics and Photonics* (SPIE, 2014), 9286, pp. 41–54.
8. J. Wojtanowski, M. Zygmunt, M. Muzal, *et al.*, "Performance verification of a LIF-LIDAR technique for stand-off detection and classification of biological agents," *Opt. Laser Technol.* **67**, 25–32 (2015).
9. I. Colomina and P. Molina, "Unmanned aerial systems for photogrammetry and remote sensing: A review," *ISPRS Journal of photogrammetry and remote sensing* **92**, 79–97 (2014).
10. A. Gholizadeh and V. Kopačková, "Detecting vegetation stress as a soil contamination proxy: A review of optical proximal and remote sensing techniques," *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* **16**(5), 2511–2524 (2019).
11. Z. Duan, Y. Li, J. Wang, *et al.*, "Aquatic environment monitoring using a drone-based fluorosensor," *Appl. Phys. B* **125**(6), 108 (2019).
12. O. Bukin, D. Y. Proshenko, A. Chekhlenok, *et al.*, "Methods for optical monitoring of oil pollution of sea water basins using unmanned aerial vehicles," *Atmos. Oceanic Opt.* **32**(4), 459–463 (2019).
13. T. G. Kaye and M. Pittman, "Fluorescence-based detection of field targets using an autonomous unmanned aerial vehicle system," *Methods Ecol. Evol.* **11**(8), 890–898 (2020).
14. Z. Kolber, D. Klimov, G. Ananyev, *et al.*, "Measuring photosynthetic parameters at a distance: laser induced fluorescence transient (LIFT) method for remote measurements of photosynthesis in terrestrial vegetation," *Photosynth. Res.* **84**(1-3), 121–129 (2005).
15. X. Wang, Z. Duan, M. Brydegaard, *et al.*, "Drone-based area scanning of vegetation fluorescence height profiles using a miniaturized hyperspectral lidar system," *Appl. Phys. B* **124**(11), 207 (2018).
16. X. Zhao, S. Shi, J. Yang, *et al.*, "Active 3D imaging of vegetation based on multi-wavelength fluorescence LiDAR," *Sensors* **20**(3), 935 (2020).
17. P. Chen, D. Pan, and Z. Mao, "Development of a portable laser-induced fluorescence system used for in situ measurements of dissolved organic matter," *Opt. Laser Technol.* **64**, 213–219 (2014).
18. L. Sun, Y. Zhang, C. Ouyang, *et al.*, "A portable UAV-based laser-induced fluorescence lidar system for oil pollution and aquatic environment monitoring," *Opt. Commun.* **527**, 128914 (2023).
19. M. Brydegaard, A. Merdasa, A. Gebru, *et al.*, "Realistic instrumentation platform for active and passive optical remote sensing," *Appl. Spectrosc.* **70**(2), 372–385 (2016).
20. R. Wiens, P. Gasda, A. Misra, *et al.*, "Airborne reconnaissance mission concept for organics in a Martian cave," in (Lunar and Planetary Institute, 2020).
21. M. N. Abedin, A. T. Bradley, S. K. Sharma, *et al.*, "Mineralogy and astrobiology detection using laser remote sensing instrument," *Appl. Opt.* **54**(25), 7598–7611 (2015).

22. C. Kölbl, F. Gebert, F. Duschek, *et al.*, “Laser based reconnaissance of major damage situations with leakage of hazardous materials,” (2018).
23. K. Cikalleshi, A. Nexha, T. Kister, *et al.*, “A printed luminescent flier inspired by plant seeds for eco-friendly physical sensing,” *Sci. Adv.* **9**(46), eadi8492 (2023).
24. B. Mazzolai, T. Kraus, N. Pirrone, *et al.*, “Towards new frontiers for distributed environmental monitoring based on an ecosystem of plant seed-like soft robots,” in *Proceedings of the Conference on Information Technology for Social Good* (2021), pp. 221–224.
25. H. Mustafa, H. A. Khan, H. Bartholomeus, *et al.*, “Design of an active laser-induced fluorescence observation system from unmanned aerial vehicles for artificial seed-like structures,” in *Remote Sensing for Agriculture, Ecosystems, and Hydrology XXIV* (SPIE, 2022), 12262, p. 1226205.
26. A. Casillas-Rubio, D. Mendez-Gonzalez, M. Laurenti, *et al.*, *Impact of Excitation Pulse Width on the Upconversion Luminescence Lifetime of NaYF₄: Yb³⁺, Er³⁺ Nanoparticles* (Nanoscale, 2024).
27. F. Huang, X. Liu, Y. Ma, *et al.*, “Origin of near to middle infrared luminescence and energy transfer process of Er³⁺/Yb³⁺ + co-doped fluorotellurite glasses under different excitations,” *Sci. Rep.* **5**(1), 8233 (2015).
28. L. Fu, Y. Wu, and T. Fu, “Determination of absorption cross-section of RE³⁺ + in upconversion powder materials: Application to β-NaYF₄: Er³⁺,” *J. Lumin.* **245**, 118758 (2022).
29. Y. Liu, Z. Zhou, S. Zhang, *et al.*, “Mechanisms of upconversion luminescence of Er³⁺-doped NaYF₄ via 980 and 1530 nm excitation,” *Nanomaterials* **11**(10), 2767 (2021).
30. H. X. Mai, Y. W. Zhang, L. D. Sun, *et al.*, “Highly efficient multicolor up-conversion emissions and their mechanisms of monodisperse NaYF₄: Yb, Er core and core/shell-structured nanocrystals,” *J. Phys. Chem. C* **111**(37), 13721–13729 (2007).
31. X. Xu, Z. Wang, J. Hou, *et al.*, “Upconversion Emission and Dual-Mode Sensing Characteristics of NaYF₄: Yb³⁺/Er³⁺ Microcrystals at High and Ultralow Temperatures,” *Nanomaterials* **14**(10), 871 (2024).
32. D. A. Leonard, J. F. Shaw, C. Smith, *et al.*, “Compact hybrid IR/UV biological sensor,” in *Air Monitoring and Detection of Chemical and Biological Agents* (SPIE, 1999), 3533, pp. 164–173.
33. T. K. Christopoulos and E. P. Diamandis, “Fluorescence immunoassays,” in *Immunoassay* (Academic Press, 1996), pp. 309–335.
34. T. G. Mayerhöfer, S. Pahlow, and J. Popp, “The Bouguer-Beer-Lambert law: Shining light on the obscure,” *ChemPhysChem* **21**(18), 2029–2046 (2020).
35. C. D. Mobley, ed., *The Oceanic Optics Book* (International Ocean Colour Coordinating Group (IOCCG), 2022).
36. S. G. Lambert, “Design and analysis study of a spacecraft optical transceiver package” (No, JPL-9950-1240) (1985).
37. W. K. Marshall and B. D. Burk, *Received Optical Power Calculations for Optical Communications Link Performance Analysis* (The telecommunications and data acquisition report, 1986).
38. A. G. Alkholidi and K. S. Altowij, “Free space optical communications—Theory and practices,” *Contemporary Issues in Wireless Communications* **5**, 159–212 (2014).
39. M. Grabner and V. Kvicera, “The wavelength dependent model of extinction in fog and haze for free space optical communication,” *Opt. Express* **19**(4), 3379–3386 (2011).
40. C. Chen, “Attenuation of electromagnetic radiation by haze, fog, clouds, and rain,” *Spie Milestone Series MS 133*, 283–298 (1997).
41. H. Kaushal and G. Kaddoum, “Optical Communication in Space: Challenges and Mitigation Techniques,” *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials* **19**(1), 57–96 (2017).
42. M. Pollnau, D. R. Gamelin, S. R. Lüthi, *et al.*, “Power dependence of upconversion luminescence in lanthanide and transition-metal-ion systems,” *Phys. Rev. B* **61**(5), 3337–3346 (2000).
43. K. Li, D. Zhu, and C. Yue, “Exceptional low-temperature fluorescence sensing properties in novel KBaY(MoO₄)₃:Yb³⁺, Ho³⁺ materials based on FIR of Ho³⁺ transitions 5 F₅(1) → 5 I₈/5 S₂ → 5 I₈,” *J. Mater. Chem. C* **10**(17), 6603–6610 (2022).
44. M. C. Fuchs, J. Beyer, S. Lorenz, *et al.*, “A spectral library for laser-induced fluorescence analysis as a tool for rare earth element identification,” *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **13**(9), 4465–4483 (2021).
45. L. G. Coppel, N. Johansson, and M. Neuman, “Angular dependence of fluorescence from turbid media,” *Opt. Express* **23**(15), 19552–19564 (2015).
46. J. Yang, Y. Cheng, L. Du, *et al.*, “Analyzing the effect of the incidence angle on chlorophyll fluorescence intensity based on laser-induced fluorescence lidar,” *Opt. Express* **27**(9), 12541–12550 (2019).
47. M. S. Patterson, B. C. Wilson, and D. R. Wyman, “The propagation of optical radiation in tissue I. Models of radiation transport and their application,” *Lasers Med. Sci.* **6**(2), 155–168 (1991).
48. J. R. Lakowicz, *Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy* (Springer, 2006).
49. A. Nefian, U. Y. Wong, M. Dille, *et al.*, “Structured light-based hazard detection for planetary surface navigation,” in *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)* (IEEE, 2017), pp. 2665–2671.
50. E. Fišerová and M. Kubala, “Mean fluorescence lifetime and its error,” *J. Lumin.* **132**(8), 2059–2064 (2012).
51. A. Assy, H.-J. Lin, M. Schoenauer-Sebag, *et al.*, “Nanoscale thermometry with fluorescent yttrium-based Er/Yb-doped fluoride nanocrystals,” *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical* **250**, 71–77 (2016).
52. L. F. dos Santos, J. A. Galindo, K. d. O. Lima, *et al.*, “Lifetime-based luminescence thermometry from Yb³⁺/Er³⁺ codoped nanoparticles suspended in water,” *J. Lumin.* **262**, 119946 (2023).

53. A. Rafiei Miandashti, M. E. Kordesch, and H. H. Richardson, "Effect of temperature and gold nanoparticle interaction on the lifetime and luminescence of NaYF₄: Yb³⁺: Er³⁺ upconverting nanoparticles," *ACS Photonics* **4**(7), 1864–1869 (2017).
54. S. M. Ehtesham Raza, X. Wang, Y. Jin, *et al.*, "Improved thermometry via luminescence lifetime ratio of Er³⁺ and Tm³⁺ operated in the biological window," *Opt. Express* **32**(20), 35822–35831 (2024).
55. M. Lagos and R. Paredes, "Thermal quenching of fluorescence in condensed media," *Solid State Commun.* **242**, 52–56 (2016).
56. M. H. Hutchinson, J. R. Dorgan, D. M. Knauss, *et al.*, "Optical properties of polylactides," *J. Polym. Environ.* **14**(2), 119–124 (2006).
57. N. Stopikowska, P. Woźny, M. Suta, *et al.*, "Influence of excitation and detection geometry on optical temperature readouts—reabsorption effects in luminescence thermometry," *J. Mater. Chem. C* **11**(28), 9620–9627 (2023).
58. F. Martelli, S. Del Bianco, A. Ismaelli, *et al.*, "Light Propagation through and Other Diffusive Media: Theory, Solutions, and Software, SPIE Press, Bellingham," Washington USA Chap 4, (2010).
59. C. Amendola, M. Lacerenza, I. Pirovano, *et al.*, "Optical characterization of 3D printed PLA and ABS filaments for diffuse optics applications," *PLoS ONE* **16**(6), e0253181 (2021).
60. J. Feng, Q. Jiang, P. Rogin, *et al.*, "Printed soft optical waveguides of PLA copolymers for guiding light into tissue," *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **12**(18), 20287–20294 (2020).
61. K. Khosh Abady, D. Dankhar, A. Krishnamoorthi, *et al.*, "Enhancing the upconversion efficiency of NaYF₄: Yb, Er microparticles for infrared vision applications," *Sci. Rep.* **13**(1), 8408 (2023).
62. A. Petris, P. Gheorghe, and I. Rau, "Influence of continuous wave laser light at 532 nm on transmittance and on photoluminescence of DNA-CTMA-RhB solutions," *Heliyon* **9**(10), e20410 (2023).
63. J. R. Albani, "Fluorescence Quenching," in *Structure and Dynamics of Macromolecules: Absorption and Fluorescence Studies* (Elsevier, 2011).
64. V. Pilla, T. Catunda, S. M. Lima, *et al.*, "Thermal quenching of the fluorescence quantum efficiency in colquiriite crystals measured by thermal lens spectrometry," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **21**(10), 1784–1791 (2004).
65. C. M. Jones, A. Gakamsky, and J. Marques-Hueso, "The upconversion quantum yield (UCQY): a review to standardize the measurement methodology, improve comparability, and define efficiency standards," *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.* **22**(1), 810–848 (2021).
66. P. S. Solanki, S. Balabhadra, L. D. Browne, *et al.*, "Excitation wavelength dependent photoluminescence and photochromic studies of Yb³⁺/Er³⁺ + doped β– KYF₄ and β– NaYF₄ nanoparticles," *Opt. Mater.* **132**, 112783 (2022).
67. F. T. Rabouw, P. T. Prins, P. Villanueva-Delgado, *et al.*, "Quenching pathways in NaYF₄: Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ + upconversion nanocrystals," *ACS Nano* **12**(5), 4812–4823 (2018).
68. B. P. Kore, A. Kumar, L. Erasmus, *et al.*, "Energy Transfer Mechanisms and Optical Thermometry of BaMgF₄:Yb³⁺,Er³⁺ Phosphor," *Inorg. Chem.* **57**(1), 288–299 (2018).
69. H. Mustafa, "Dataset for Spectroscopic characterization of laser-induced luminescence for remote environmental thermometry," Zenodo Version 1.0 2025 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918271>.